

Supplementary material to “The effect of hypoglycaemic therapy with pioglitazone or glimepiride on the AGE/RAGE axis: a randomized prospective study”

Figure S1. Dendrogram showing the distribution of Δ glyco-oxidation parameters among patients of the two treatment groups. Ward's clustering method, values standardized by each variable. Dendrogram green color intensity is proportional to the parameter value.

Figure S2. Distribution of Δ glyco-oxidation parameters in the overall cohort of patients according to gender.

Table S1. Paired correlations (linear model) for Δ of the various parameters, considering all patients, and conditioned on Δ Weight as confounding variable.

Variable	vs Variable	Correlation coefficient <i>r</i>	<i>P</i>
Age	Δ S-RAGE	-0.210	0.080
Age	Δ AGE	-0.036	0.767
Age	Δ AGE/sRAGE	-0.016	0.894
Diabetes duration	Δ S-RAGE	0.013	0.916
Diabetes duration	Δ AGE	0.177	0.137
Diabetes duration	Δ AGE/sRAGE	0.198	0.100
Δ BMI	Δ S-RAGE	-0.104	0.392
Δ BMI	Δ AGE	0.171	0.150
Δ BMI	Δ AGE/sRAGE	0.187	0.121
Δ SBP	Δ S-RAGE	-0.213	0.077
Δ SBP	Δ AGE	-0.057	0.633
Δ SBP	Δ AGE/sRAGE	-0.043	0.725
Δ DBP	Δ S-RAGE	-0.179	0.139
Δ DBP	Δ AGE	0.067	0.573
Δ DBP	Δ AGE/sRAGE	0.145	0.231
Δ Waist	Δ S-RAGE	0.034	0.780
Δ Waist	Δ AGE	0.084	0.481
Δ Waist	Δ AGE/sRAGE	0.209	0.083
Δ eGFR	Δ S-RAGE	0.079	0.515
Δ eGFR	Δ AGE	0.080	0.507
Δ eGFR	Δ AGE/sRAGE	0.076	0.534
Δ Serum creatinine	Δ S-RAGE	-0.086	0.479
Δ Serum creatinine	Δ AGE	-0.023	0.849
Δ Serum creatinine	Δ AGE/sRAGE	-0.042	0.728
Δ HbA1c	Δ S-RAGE	0.121	0.318
Δ HbA1c	Δ AGE	-0.010	0.935
Δ HbA1c	Δ AGE/sRAGE	0.004	0.976
Δ CRP	Δ S-RAGE	0.105	0.385
Δ CRP	Δ AGE	-0.022	0.857
Δ CRP	Δ AGE/sRAGE	0.0008	0.995
10y-ASCVD risk	Δ S-RAGE	0.022	0.856
10y-ASCVD risk	Δ AGE	-0.036	0.762
10y-ASCVD risk	Δ AGE/sRAGE	-0.047	0.697

Note. Conditioned on variables: Δ Weight